

NEWSLETTER

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Workshop Brings Together Experts And Highlights Advances In AI And Next-Generation Networks

The SMARTNESS Research Center held its Year 3 Workshop online on April 16 and 17. The event brought together more than 60 participants on each of the two days and included researchers, students, and representatives from Ericsson, a strategic research partner.

The initiative served as a relevant platform for presenting results and discussing emerging technological trends.

[Read more](#)

Center Strengthens International Collaboration With FIIS-UNI Delegation From Peru

SMARTNESS welcomed a delegation from FIIS-UNI (Facultad de Ingeniería Industrial y de Sistemas at Universidad Nacional de Ingeniería – Peru), reinforcing its commitment to internationalization and to strengthening strategic partnerships.

The group was received by the Director of FEEC Unicamp, Hugo Figueroa, and had the opportunity to explore the Center’s laboratory infrastructure.

[Read more](#)

Strategic Innovation In Focus: Ericsson Delegation Visits SMARTNESS

A delegation from Ericsson, visiting from Sweden, met with researchers at SMARTNESS for a strategic agenda focused on evaluating third-year results and expanding collaboration in Artificial Intelligence (AI).

The team included Björn Johannisson, Aneta Vulgarakis, and Mikael Prytz, along with representatives from Ericsson Brazil.

[Read more](#)

Center Hosts Special Work Package Meeting With Ericsson Team In Brazil

The CPE held a special Work Packages meeting at the University of Campinas, with participation from Ericsson researchers, focusing on technical discussions of the NW2 and NW3 projects and strengthening collaboration between academia and industry in robotics, Artificial Intelligence, and advanced connectivity.

[Read more](#)

Researchers Visit Indaiatuba For A Co-Creation Agenda And High-Impact 5G Demos With Ericsson

Researchers from SMARTNESS visited Ericsson's 5G Open Innovation Center in Indaiatuba for a technology immersion with a clear goal: turning 5G connectivity into real-world impact for society.

The visit strengthened the bridge between applied research and industry challenges, opening new avenues for the co-creation of proofs of concept (PoCs) and experiments.

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YEARLY SCIENTIFIC REPORT #03 (RC3)

Title: SMART Networks and Services for 2030 (SMARTNESS)
 FAPESP Grant #: 2021/00199-8
 Support type: Research Grants – Research Centers in Engineering Program
 Host Institution: Universidade Estadual de Campinas (UNICAMP)
 Duration: April/2023 - March/2033
 Scientific Report period: April/2025 - March/2026 (Year 03)

SMARTNESS Principal Investigator (PI) and Director:
 Prof. Christian Rodolfo Esteve Rothenberg (UNICAMP)

Submission Of The Year 3 Scientific Report (RC3)

The Year 3 Scientific Report (RC3) of the SMARTNESS Engineering Research Center (FAPESP Grant No. 2021/00199-8), covering the period from April 2025 to March 2026, was submitted in April 2026.

The document presents the main results and activities carried out during the period, meeting the requirements of FAPESP and ensuring the continuity of the project. The public version of the report is available on [Zenodo](#).

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS & DISCLAIMER

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